

Visual Interpretation of Dragonfly Wine's New Label in a Hermeneutic Perspective

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Abstract

The wine industry in Indonesia has been growing rapidly, despite the country not being a major grape producer. PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk., as a pioneer in Indonesia's wine industry, continues to embrace local values in its products, including Dragonfly Wines. In 2021, the Dragonfly label underwent a design transformation, shifting from a minimalist aesthetic to a more expressive and colorful look, aligning with a younger and more dynamic target market. This change has led to various visual interpretations that influence the product's image and consumer perception. This study analyzes the transformation of the Dragonfly Wines label through Jacques Derrida's hermeneutic approach to understand how visual meaning evolves alongside design changes. The research employs a qualitative descriptive method, focusing on the analysis of visual communication design elements, including illustration, color, and typography. The findings reveal that the dragonfly illustration, as the central element of the new label, symbolizes transformation and adaptability, while the use of brighter colors reflects energy and enthusiasm. The design change also impacts consumer perception, with many assuming that the new label represents a different product or a reformulated version. This study reaffirms that visual elements in branding play a crucial role in shaping product identity and perception. The transformation of the Dragonfly Wines label is not merely an aesthetic strategy but a branding approach that adapts to market dynamics while preserving the essence of the brand identity.

Keywords: *branding, label design, hermeneutics, visual interpretation, Dragonfly Wines.*

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Introduction

The beverage industry in Indonesia continues to grow, including the wine industry, an alcoholic drink commonly associated with Western culture. Although Indonesia is not known as a major wine-producing country, the industry has expanded, particularly in Bali, where the climate supports the cultivation of certain grape varieties.

PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk., established in 1994 and based in Sanur, Bali, is a pioneer in Indonesia's wine industry. The company emphasizes local identity in its products, including the selection of grape varieties. One of its notable products is Dragonfly Wines, first introduced in 2019. This wine offers a sweet taste with a low alcohol content of 8%. Dragonfly Wines comes in two variants, such as Dragonfly Moscato and Cabernet Shiraz, made from grapes grown in PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.'s vineyards in South Australia and processed in Bali. To establish a distinct identity for this wine, PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk. initially designed an elegant label highlighting the product name and Dragonfly logo.

In 2021, PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk. redesigned the Dragonfly label to align with the younger, more creative, and dynamic target market. The new label features a bolder visual exploration with expressive illustrations

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and a more vibrant color palette, that significantly different from their previous design that has minimalist design. This transformation was not merely a marketing strategy but also had a considerable impact on the product's image and consumer perception. Many consumers assumed that the new label indicated a different product, a new variant, or even a modification in formula and taste. This phenomenon highlights the crucial role of visual elements in label design in shaping consumer perception of a product's identity and the connection to the master brand.

According to Ibrahim (2025), visual elements such as logos, colors, and typography play a significant role in shaping brand image. Strong branding fosters consumer trust and enhances customer loyalty. Additionally, product packaging significantly influences consumer perceptions of quality and value. An attractive and high-quality packaging design can elevate consumer perceptions of product quality (Ariodutho, 2023:213). Some of these studies have discussed the influence of visual elements in branding on consumer perception and how packaging design can influence purchasing decisions. However, there are no studies that specifically address how label transformation, particularly of local wine labels in Indonesia, can change visual interpretation in the context of visual communication design and their relationship to the main brand. Therefore, this research aims to analyze the transformation of Dragonfly's label using hermeneutic approach, to understand how this visual transformation is perceived and interpreted in the context of branding and brand identity. The hermeneutic approach was used to understand how the meaning of the visual branding elements evolved along with the design changes. This method allows for an in-depth examination of how consumers interpreted the changes to the Dragonfly label in relation to PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.,'s core brand identity.

Materials and Methods

The research method used in this research is a qualitative descriptive method, with analysis based on data obtained by the researcher using a Hermeneutic approach. Hermeneutics is a science or art of interpretation of a text (Susanto, 2016:2). It is considered a science because it requires a systematic and logical process of meaning-making that is rational and testable. At the same time, Hermeneutics regarded as an art because it involves presenting interpretations in a meaningful and aesthetically compelling way. Hermeneutics, as the "art of understanding," always involves a fusion between the subjective dimension of comprehension and the recognition of the linguistic nature of what is being interpreted or the objective dimension (Simamora, 2005:3).

This study adopts Jacques Derrida's hermeneutic approach. Derrida states that the meaning of a text is always change depending on the context and the reader's interpretation. According to Derrida, every text has the potential to deconstruct itself, meaning the text can always be read and understood in multiple ways. He emphasizes that in understanding the meaning of the text should not continue to maintain the old meaning (already existing), and impose the meaning as the true meaning. Instead, new truths must emerge from previous meanings and be reshaped into new interpretations. Once these new meanings are found, interpreters must refrain from claiming them as absolute or definitive truths. Derrida's perspective constantly encourages the emergence of new meanings by challenging existing interpretations, allowing unexpected meanings to surface (Tana, 2019).

For Derrida, no text is bound by a transcendental foundation. A text is always correlated with the context, which creates continuous opportunities for new interpretations that interconnect between text and context (Udang, 2019:122). This means that although different individuals may engage with the same text (or reality), they can generate diverse interpretations and understandings. This celebration of plurality is one of the fundamental principles of Derrida's deconstructionist approach.

Results and Discussion

The label is one of the most crucial elements of a product. It is not only a medium for conveying information but also serves as an advertisement and a key aspect of product branding. According to

Kotler (2000:478), the functions of a label are as follows: (1) identifying the product or brand; (2) determining the product class; (3) providing information about the product, such as its manufacturer, place and date of production, contents, usage instructions, and safety guidelines; and (4) promoting the product through visually appealing designs. In the case of wine products, labels typically include details about the brand, variety, vintage year, producer, region of production, and more. Wine labels are also widely used as a marketing tool to attract consumer attention and assist them in selecting a wine that aligns with their preferences.

In the previous label design, Dragonfly Moscato and Cabernet Shiraz emphasized the product logo and essential information about the wine. The color scheme was limited to red and orange, creating a simple yet elegant look, much like the traditional aesthetic of wine packaging.

Figure 1. The Previous Label of Dragonfly Wine
 Source: Dragonfly Instagram @dragonflywines. 2019

Dragonfly redesigned its label in 2021, adopting a more modern approach by emphasizing illustrations on the label. This significant transformation introduces a Hermeneutic process, leading to various interpretations of the meanings embedded in the new label. In Derrida’s Hermeneutic approach, a sign or symbol used in a design is always open to multiple interpretations. The author interprets the new Dragonfly label as an object or text to uncover its meaning. Additionally, the author seeks interpretations from the creators to understand the meaning based on their perspective and intent. The interpretations obtained are then reanalyzed to generate new meanings.

Figure 2. The Author's Hermeneutic Approach

Source: Author's Documentation. 2025

Interpretation of The New Dragonfly Wine Label Based on Visual Communication Design Elements

The Hermeneutic process applied to the new Dragonfly Wine label involves interpreting the label based on its visual elements.

Figure 3. The New Label of Dragonfly Wine

Source: Author's Documentation. 2025

Below is the interpretation obtained by the author using a hermeneutic approach to the new Dragonfly label:

1. Illustration

Illustration serves as a key element and focal point in the new Dragonfly label. The author observes that the illustration displayed on the label consists of several components, such as:

Figure 4. Breakdown of Illustrations on the Dragonfly Label

Sources: Author's Documentation. 2025

a. *Dragonfly Illustration*

The dragonfly illustration appears to blend with other elements; however, the author can still identify the structure of the dragonfly's head and body. The head is represented by three curved lines, indicating the head and two eyes. The thorax, located in the middle of the body, features four wavy wings that merge with the surrounding illustrations, followed by a long, curved abdomen. The author identifies the dragonfly as the primary element, as it directly corresponds to the product's name, Dragonfly. The shape of the dragonfly is adapted to the illustrator's artistic style while also aligning with the image of the creative consumer that the brand aims to highlight.

The way the dragonfly appears integrated with other illustration elements is interpreted as a representation of adaptation within the colorful ecosystem, symbolizing the joy and vitality. Additionally, the dragonfly is often interpreted as a symbol of transformation and change, because of their metamorphic life cycle, from egg to larva, then pupa, and finally to adulthood. The dragonfly is also a symbol of courage and strength, commonly associated with persistence and the ability to thrive in ever-changing environments. This is further reflected in the diverse patterns within the dragonfly's form, which signify continuous transformation throughout the lifecycle.

b. *Sun Illustration*

A sun illustration is placed in the upper right corner of the label. The sun is universally associated with bright light and a source of energy. The dragonfly appears to be flying towards the sun, symbolizing a pursuit of light and energy, essential for growth and survival.

c. *Ilustrasi of Clouds, Plants, and Water as the Dragonfly's Ecosystem*

The illustration represents the habitat and ecosystem of the dragonfly's life cycle. Some dragonflies inhabit areas near clean water sources surrounded by lush green plants. The presence of dragonflies in an environment often serves as a bioindicator, signifying that the surrounding area still has clean water. In this label illustration, the depiction of the dragonfly's ecosystem is designed with interconnected elements, creating a sense of unity among the visual components. This integration conveys the harmony and beauty of the dragonfly's natural habitat.

2. Color

In this new label, Dragonfly retains the same background colors as its previous label. The background color for Dragonfly Moscato is bright orange, which conveys a cheerful and lively impression. Orange is associated with happiness, energy, enthusiasm, and joy (Rustan, 2009:58). However, orange can also evoke a psychological response that emphasizes an inexpensive product (Pujiriyanto, 2005:48). Meanwhile, the background color for Dragonfly Cabernet Shiraz is red, which appears luxurious, premium, and strong. Based on the meaning of color, red is often associated with passion, warmth, strength, ambition, and energy (Rustan, 2009:58). However, depending on the context and individual experiences, red can also symbolize danger or warning. These two background colors are eye-catching and create a sense of brightness, which, according to the author, makes the product more noticeable from a distance and sparks consumer curiosity.

In terms of the colors used in the illustration, the author observes that Dragonfly incorporates a variety of pastel tones. Additionally, the label features a layered coloring technique similar to *Sigar Mangsi*. *Sigar Mangsi* is a traditional Balinese coloring technique that employs a layer-by-layer approach to create a smooth color gradient. This technique builds colors from dark to light, and vice versa (Pastika, 2008:110). The use of this technique gives the label a sense of depth and volume. For the author, this coloring technique also reinforces the perception that Dragonfly is a product originating from a Balinese wine company.

3. Typography

The label features two types of typography, such as Script for the product name, Dragonfly and Serif for the information located at the bottom. This choice of typefaces gives the label a rigid, classic, and formal

appearance. The author observes a certain ambiguity between the illustration and the typography used on the label. The illustration appears vibrant and dynamic, while the typography is structured and overly formal. This contrast creates an interesting tension between playfulness and sophistication in the overall design.

Figure 5. Typography and Text Composition on Dragonfly Label
 Source: Author's Documentation. 2025

4. Copywriting or Text

The text displayed on the label, apart from the product name, includes details such as the type of wine, grape variety, year of production, alcohol content, volume, BPOM code, production location, and a pregnancy warning. The author observes that the dominance of text is very low compared to the illustration. Consumers are more likely to focus on the illustration rather than the textual information due to its small size and placement at the bottom of the label. Based on the author's interpretation, in terms of visual hierarchy, the new Dragonfly wine label significantly deviates from standard wine labeling conventions. This label prioritizes illustration as the main visual attraction, which overwhelmingly dominates the space on the label. Meanwhile, crucial information about the wine's origin, grape variety, alcohol content, year, volume, and other essential details is presented in a much smaller font.

This approach challenges the conventional structure of wine labeling, which typically emphasizes key product details. Standard wine labels generally display important information such as the brand name, address, grape variety, region of origin, alcohol content, year of production, net volume, sulfite and allergy indications, and health warnings. However, in this case, consumers are more likely to focus on the illustration rather than reading the product information.

Overall, the visual elements, particularly the illustrations on this new label, create a vastly different impression from the overall branding of PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk. The company has long maintained an elegant image, both in its corporate branding and across its wine products. In contrast, the Dragonfly label conveys a sense of cheerfulness, relaxation, vibrancy, and even childlike playfulness. The childlike impression primarily comes from the pastel colors used in the label design. Pastel colors are commonly associated with children's characteristics, as they motivate activity, joy, and creativity. Additionally, pastel colors are considered visually safe for children, because they are not glaring, do not cause eye fatigue, pleasant, and non-intimidating (Sari, 2004:32). This playful visual identity creates a stark contrast to the typical wine imagery, that has been reserved for 21 years and above.

Figure 6. General Wine Label Standards

Source: Bluelabelpackaging. 2025

To better understand the intended meaning behind this new label, the author also conducted an interview with PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.’s designer. Since the company itself was the main initiator of the label change, the interview aimed to clarify their objectives. For the new Dragonfly label, PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk. collaborated with a Balinese illustrator, Monez. The interview revealed that the label redesign was intended to align with the sweet taste profile of Dragonfly Moscato and Cabernet Shiraz. This sweetness was meant to be visually reflected through a modern and dynamic style, appealing more directly to young consumers. According to PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk., the sweetness of Dragonfly wine makes it suitable for parties, pairing with any type of food, or simply enjoyed as a refreshing drink after a long day. As a result, their target consumers for Dragonfly include young, creative, flexible, socially active, and productive individuals. Monez was selected as the illustrator because of his signature style, which prominently features bright colors, a perfect match for Dragonfly’s youthful target audience. Consequently, the color palette for the Dragonfly label uses vibrant hues. Vibrant colors, often associated with boldness, enthusiasm, and high contrast, create a modern, expressive, and dramatic feel. Moreover, vibrant colors help emphasize the illustrations (Novia, 2016:5).

The choice of the dragonfly elements as the central illustration is directly tied to the product’s name, Dragonfly. Additionally, the philosophy of the dragonfly aligns with the brand’s narrative, as dragonflies are known as indicators of a clean ecosystem. Dragonflies play a crucial role in the environment, serving as bioindicators of water quality. Their presence often signals a healthy and unpolluted habitat. Beyond its ecological significance, the dragonfly also carries positive symbolic meanings, representing happiness, good fortune, and personal transformation. When comparing the author’s interpretation with the brand’s intended meaning, it becomes evident that there are differences in how the visual communication elements on the new Dragonfly label are perceived.

Table 1. Comparison of Visual Communication Design Elements

Visual Communication Design Elements	Author/Interpreter’s Perspective	Brand Owner’s Perspective (PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.)
Illustration	The dragonfly and its habitat appear as a unified composition, conveying a sense of happiness, creativity, and strength. The illustration is visually aesthetic.	The illustration represents the dragonfly as the icon of Dragonfly wine, symbolizing its presence in a healthy and fertile ecosystem.

Color	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The red and orange background appears bright and eye-catching. • The coloring technique resembles <i>Sigar Mangsi</i>, a Balinese artistic style, subtly indicating local identity. • The colors in the illustration appear pastel-like, which is commonly associated with children rather than the vibrant, expressive, and dramatic hues expected for a wine label. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The color scheme remains the same as the previous label. • The colors are adjusted to match the characteristics of the target audience—young consumers who are creative, dynamic, sociable, and productive. • The illustration features vibrant colors, symbolizing boldness.
Typography	The use of Script and Serif fonts gives a formal and rigid impression, which contradicts the intended modern, trendy, and dynamic brand image.	The Script and Serif fonts align with PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.'s elegant branding concept.
Copywriting	The text appears very small, making the label seem solely focused on the illustration.	The displayed information is sufficient and complies with wine labeling requirements.
<p>From these two interpretations come the positive and negative meanings of Dragonfly's new label, such as:</p> <p>Positive Meanings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduces innovation in wine labeling, departing from conventional label designs. • The visually attractive and eye-catching label piques curiosity about the wine's taste. <p>Negative Meanings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The branding contradicts PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.'s established elegant image, potentially leading consumers to mistake Dragonfly as an unrelated product. • The label design does not strongly indicate that the product is for consumers aged 21 and above. Instead, it leans towards a younger audience, even resembling a children's beverage. 		

Source: Author's Documentation. 2025

Conclusion

PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk., through its Dragonfly Moscato and Cabernet Shiraz products, attempts to break away from modernist conventions and shift towards postmodernism in the sense of deconstructive transformation. According to Derrida, this deconstruction is a form of metaphysical identification. This metaphysical deconstruction is carried out through collaboration with a Balinese illustrator, yet different interpretations arise from various perspectives. PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.'s effort in conducting this metaphysical deconstruction represents a novel approach in wine labeling. However, it appears somewhat misaligned, as interpreters are drawn primarily to its visual appeal, rather than perceiving it as an integrated representation of PT. Hatten Bali, Tbk.'s established brand identity, one that emphasizes elegance and Balinese locality. The new label introduces a different image, portraying creativity, cheerfulness, and a party-friendly vibe. Interestingly, Dragonfly's new label presents a fresh perspective, demonstrating that a wine label does not necessarily have to depict traditional wine-related elements such as grapes, but can instead incorporate elements tailored to the characteristics of its target audience. By applying Derrida's hermeneutic approach, the author realizes that a visual communication design piece does not have a fixed, absolute meaning; rather, it remains open to multiple interpretations. Therefore, before drawing conclusions about the meaning of a design, we must consider it from various perspectives, consider the social and cultural contexts, as well as the unique experiences and perceptions of each individual in interpreting the design's meaning.

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